

Supplementary Table S1: List of primers used in this work

Gene-TE	Allele	Genbank Acc. CDS	Sequence 5'-3' Forward Oligo	Sequence 5'-3' Reverse Oligo	Amplicon length
<i>SIDD44</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> X	AJ631230	AACAAGTCAATTCGTGCATTTTCG	GTGATCCGAATAGTGTGACTCGA	150
<i>SIDD44</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> Y	AJ631231	TGTGGGTTAATAGATGGGGAAAGG	ACTCACATTTTCAAATCTTGTTCT	157
<i>SI4</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> Y	AJ310659	TATTATCATCAATCTCAATACTCAGATCTGTTC	GATGATCTAGTTAGATTATAATCTGGGTCATTG	183
<i>SI7</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> Y	EU561060	CGATATTTACTAAAACGTGTCGATATAAATCAG	GTGTTATTCCTTCCTTGCTTTGTTTACTTCTA	100
<i>SIAP3</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> X	AB519802	AAAGAGGCTCATTGTCATACTACA	TGGAAAGTAGTAAGTGGATGTTAACT	164
<i>SIAP3</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> Y	AB519801	ACCCGAAATAGACCCGAAACC	TTTGAGATGATTAGACATTACGTAACT	101
<i>SISs</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> X	AY705437	AAAGGGCATTAAACAAAATCCG	ACAAGTTTGATTATTTGAATTTCCGGT	101
<i>SISs</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> Y	AY705438	AGGGTAAAGACACAGTTTCTTCT	TCCATGTCTTACAAAACGCAATCA	119
<i>SI3</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> X	AJ631223	GCTAAACCATTGGAGATACCCATG	ATAAGTTCATTTTAAGTTGTGGGCCA	100
<i>SI4</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> X	AJ310660	ATTGACTGAGAAGTGAGAAAGTACTCGTAAGTC	ATTGAAGAATTTACAGTGAAAAGAAGAGAAGAC	122
<i>SI7</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> X	EU561058	GGCATAATATCTTTTGTGAGTTTATATATGTCG	CCGGTAGAGTTACTTTAATGGAGAATATTTATT	306
<i>SI3</i>	<i>S. latifolia</i> Y	AJ631224	TAATCTCTACTCACCTTAATCAAACCG	ACTCGGCCGATTACCCAG	91
<i>AngelaCL1</i>			TGCGATCACAACCTGTTGATCA	TTTACCCAGGGCCAATGCAT	700
<i>AngelaCL7</i>			TGCACCCAAGACGATCTGAG	GAGCTGGTGCCTCCACAAA	796
<i>AthilaCL10</i>			GACCAAGACGCAACTCCAGA	TCAAACACATGAGGCGGGAA	839
<i>AthilaCL3</i>			TACCGGAGTCTCCTTGCTCA	GCACTAGGGTGTGATGGGTT	905
<i>OgreCL11</i>			TTCCCAATGCTTGTAGGAG	ATCGACTCGAGGTTCTTTTCG	369
<i>OgreCL5</i>			ACAGCCAGAACTCACCTTG	GGAGTCGCCACCAATTTTAA	769
<i>OgreCL6</i>			ACCGGGTTCAAATACCCATT	CCCGTTCGAATCCACTTTA	638
<i>RetandCL9</i>			GGCATATCCGCGTACTCACA	TTCGGGGTCACTTTATGGGC	826
<i>TekayCL4</i>			GTTCCTTGCCTCGAGGGTAA	ACATCCCAGCTAGTCCCAGT	785

Supplementary Table S2. Transition patterns, specific detector settings and sources of standards for analyzed deoxynucleosides.

compound name	ionization mode	nominal molecular mass (Da)	pseudomolecular ion formulation	nominal parent ion (Da)	nominal daughter ion (Da)	ESI capillary (kV)	ESI cone (V)	collision energy (eV)	standard source
5-(hydroxymethyl)-2'-deoxycytidine	positive	257	[M+H] ⁺	258	124	1.2	15	10	Berry & Associates
[D ₃]-5-(hydroxymethyl)-2'-deoxycytidine	positive	260	[(M+3)+H] ⁺	261	127	1.2	15	10	Toronto Research Chemicals
5-formyl-2'-deoxycytidine	negative	255	[M-H] ⁻	254	121	3.5	28	18	Berry & Associates
[¹³ C ₁₀ , ¹⁵ N ₂]-5-formyl-2'-deoxycytidine	negative	267	[(M+12)-H] ⁻	266	128	3.5	28	18	own synthesis
5-carboxy-2'-deoxycytidine	negative	271	[M-H] ⁻	270	110	3.5	20	20	Berry & Associates
[¹³ C ₁₀ , ¹⁵ N ₂]-5-carboxy-2'-deoxycytidine	negative	283	[(M+12)-H] ⁻	282	116	3.5	20	20	own synthesis

Supplementary Figure S1: qRT-PCR results for each antibody after immunoprecipitation in male and female plants. IN DNA Vs IP DNA (IN DNA: Input DNA, IP DNA: Immunoprecipitated DNA) The binary vector pCAMBIA-2301 was used to generate an amplicon of 389bp replacing the cytosine in the PCR reaction for the appropriate modified nucleoside (5-Methyl-2'-deoxycytidine, 5-Hydroxy-2'-deoxycytidine, 5-Formyl-2'-deoxycytidine and 5-Carboxy-2'-deoxycytidine) for each immunoprecipitation. n = 3. Asterisks represent statistical differences (* = $p < 0.05$) according to Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test ($p > 0.05$)

Supplementary Figure S2. Negative control of oxi-mCs immunofluorescence. “DAPI” staining of nuclei and chromosome in blue and “Antibody” - with the fluorescence generated by unspecific binding of the secondary antibodies. Microscope magnification is 63x. Bars are 10 μ

Supplementary Figure S3. Immunodetection of oxi-mCs in metaphase chromosomes of *S. latifolia* male. DAPI is represented in blue, Antibody shows immunofluorescence signal and Merge represents signal overlay. The bar represents 10 μ m.

Supplementary Figure S4. Immunodetection of oxi-mCs in metaphasic chromosomes of *S. latifolia* female. DAPI is represented in blue, Antibody shows immunofluorescence signal and Merge represents signal overlay. The bar represents 10 μ m.

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5mC+5hmC

♀

5mC+5hmC

Supplementary Figure S5. Immunodetection of 5mC and 5hmC in *S. latifolia* male and female metaphasic chromosomes. DAPI is represented in blue, 5mC is represented in green and 5hmC is represented in red. The bar represents 10 μ m.

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5mC+5fC

♀

5mC+5fC

Supplementary Figure S6. Immunodetection of 5mC and 5fC in *S. latifolia* male and female metaphasic chromosomes. DAPI is represented in blue, 5mC is represented in green and 5fC is represented in red. The bar represents 10 μ m.